

EMOTIONAL EFFECT IN LITERARY TRANSLATION: CAN IT BE PRESERVED?

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The preservation of emotional effect in literary translation is challenging, mainly focusing on the difficulties translators face in conveying the aesthetic and emotive dimensions of a literary text across languages. Literary translation is more than linguistic transfer, delving into the emotional tone, atmosphere, stylistic nuance, which represents a more complex task. When it comes to literary translation theory, particularly the works of Susan Bassnett, explores how this process necessitates finding exact linguistic, cultural and cognitive constraints that can change emotional responses in target-language readers. Using chosen emotionally charged parts from a literary novel as a case study, the research analyzes word choices, stylistic changes, and cultural adaptation strategies given in translation. The findings suggest that emotional effect can be partially maintained through dynamic equivalence, stylistic compensation, and culturally sensitive translation strategies; however, transferring full emotional expression in literary texts is rarely achievable due to linguistic, cultural, and aesthetic differences between source and target languages.

Emotional effect in literature is one of the most important and complex elements, as literature itself is not merely a transmission of certain information but a representation of human feelings, psychological conditions, and aesthetics aspects. In most literary works, emotions are given through stylistic devices, imagery, tone, narrative voice, and cultural symbolism, all of which add to the emotional entertainment of the reader. Therefore, translating literary text is beyond its linguistic accuracy but more about its maintenance of the original emotional atmosphere and artistic impact.

Scholars in literary translations field also argue that emotional effect is shaped by cultural perception. What is perceived as restrained emotion in one culture can be actually interpreted as emotionally weak in another, leading translators to adapt tone, intensifiers, and expressive language. As a result, translators use strategies and methods such as modulation, domestication, and stylistic compensation to preserve the emotional intensity of the original text while ensuring readability and cultural relevance in the TL.

"Invisibility" is the term I will use to describe the translator's situation and activity in contemporary Anglo-American culture. It refers to two mutually determining phenomena: one is an illusionistic effect of discourse, of the translator's own manipulation of English; the other is the practice of reading and evaluating translations that has long prevailed in the United Kingdom and the United States, among other cultures, both English and foreign language. A translated text, whether prose or poetry, fiction or nonfiction, is judged acceptable by most publishers, reviewers, and readers when it reads fluently, when the absence of any linguistic or stylistic peculiarities makes it seem transparent, giving the appearance that it reflects the foreign writer's personality or intention or the essential meaning of the foreign text—the appearance, in other words, that the translation is not in fact a translation, but the "original."

The illusion of transparency is an effect of fluent discourse, of the translator's effort to ensure easy readability by adhering to current usage, maintaining continuous syntax, fixing a precise meaning. What is so remarkable here is that this illusory effect conceals the numerous conditions under which the translation is made, starting with the translator's crucial intervention in the foreign text. The more fluent the translation, the more invisible the translator, and, presumably, the more visible the writer or meaning of the foreign text¹.

Most translators judge the success of a translation largely on the degree to which it 'doesn't read like a translation.' The object is to render Language A into Language B in a way that leaves as little evidence as possible of the process. In this view, a reader might be unaware he/she was reading a translation unless alerted to the fact. Whether adopting this perspective or not, upon beginning a project the translator must decide to what point transparency is a desideratum. Although the majority of readers hold it to be perhaps the single most important aspect of a 'good' translation, the view among translators, especially academics, is less unanimous. Scholars are more receptive to a visible role for theory in the production of a translation, and this raises the question of how much translation theory you need to be a translator².

Anne Cluysenaar, in her book on literary stylistics, makes some important points about translation. The translator, she believes, should not work with general precepts when determining what to preserve or parallel from the SL text, but should work with an eye 'on each individual structure, whether it be prose or verse', since 'each structure will lay stress on certain linguistic features or levels and not on others' She goes on to analyze C. Day Lewis' translation of Valéry's poem, *Les pas* and comes to the conclusion that the translation does not work because the translator 'was working without an adequate theory of literary translation'. What Day Lewis has done, she feels, is to have ignored the relation of parts to each other and to the whole and that his translation is, in short, 'a case of perceptual "bad form"'. The remedy for such inadequacies is also proposed: what is needed, says Cluysenaar, 'is a description of the dominant structure of every individual work to be translated'³.

The translator, then, first reads/translates in the SL and then, through a further process of decoding, translates the text into the TL language. In this he is not doing less than the reader of the SL text alone, he is actually doing more, for the SL text is being approached through more than one set of systems. It is therefore quite foolish to argue that the task of the translator is to translate but not to interpret, as if the two were separate exercises. The interlingual translation is bound to reflect the translator's own creative interpretation of the SL text. Moreover, the degree to which the translator reproduces the form, metre, rhythm, tone, register, etc. of the SL text, will be as much determined by the TL system as by the SL system and will also depend on the function of the translation. If, as in the case of the Loeb Classics Library, the translation is intended as a line-by-line crib on the facing page to the SL text, then this factor will be a major criterion. If, on the other hand, the SL text is being reproduced for readers with no knowledge either of the language or the socio literary conventions of the SL system, then the translation will be constructed in terms other than those employed in the bilingual version⁴.

¹Venuti L. *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation*. 1995. – P. 14.

²Landers C. E. *Literary Translation: A Practical Guide*. 2001. – P. 49.

³Cluysenaar A. *Introduction to Literary Stylistics*. 1976. – P. 49.

⁴Bassnett S. *Translation Studies*. – 3rd ed., 2002. – P. 86.

All in all, unlike technical or specialized translation, literary translation requires not only linguistic competence but also the ability to reproduce the emotional atmosphere and stylistic depth of the source text. The article aims to examine the extent to which emotional effect can be preserved in literary translation. By applying key concepts from literary translation theory and analyzing selected emotionally expressive pages with their Uzbek translated versions, the study seeks to identify the strategies used by translators to maintain emotional resonance in the target text.

The primary material for analysis consists of selected emotionally significant letters from Johann Wolfgang von Goethe's novel "The Sorrows of Young Werther" and their Uzbek translation, which was translated directly from the German original version.

The genre being epistolary, the novel makes it especially suitable for analyzing emotional expression, as the narration is mainly through personal letters of Werther, representing mental state, emotional intensity, and inner conflicts.

A comparative method is used to identify changes in emotional coloring between the source text and the target text (Uzbek translation). The primary focus is on the translation process where the translator paid attention to emotional intensity, whether she preserved, softened, intensified or neutralized it.

In this letter, Werther describes his first deep emotional impression of Charlotte. This part is featured in exclamatory structures, romantic idealization, and emotion-related metaphors. A comparative analysis of the English version of the text and the Uzbek translation ("Yosh Verterning iztiroblari") shows that the translator prioritizes emotional resonance over literary equivalence.

For instance, the original exclamation "*An angel! Nonsense!*" is transferred in Uzbek as "*Farishta! ... Ha!... Ha.*" This translation shows a rise in emotional intensity through repetition and punctuation, which strengthens the expressive tone of the narrative, reflecting a culturally adapted poetic expression that maintains emotional depth of the ST compared to its literal lexical structure.

Furthermore, the sentence "*I am happy and contended mortal, but a poor historian*" is translated into a more lyrical Uzbek construction; "*Shunday mamnun va baxtlimanki, buni ifodalashga qalamim o'jiz.*" This example illustrates how the translator conveys emotional vibe and stylistic elegance, aligning with the principles of expressive text translation proposed by Bassnett.

A moment that shows feminism in Charlotte's perspective, where Charlotte attempt to regulate Werther's emotional excess. In the English version, she says, "*Be a man, and conquer an unhappy attachment toward a creature who can do nothing but pity you.*" This line shows a clear gender ideology, masculinity which is associated with self-control, rationality and emotional suppression. However, in Uzbek, it is translated as "*Yigit bo'ling! ...Sizga faqat achinishgina qo'lidan keladigan kimsaga befoyda bog'lanishdan voz keching!*", which could have been interpreted as: "*Erkak bo'lsangizchi/ Erkak bo'ling! ... Sizga faqat achinishgina qo'lidan keladigan kimsaga befoyda bog'lamib qolishdan voz keching ortiq!*" The word choice of "*Yigit bo'ling!*" doesn't sound natural for Uzbek readers, since we mainly use the word "*Erkak bo'ling!*" in our daily speech.

Moreover, Werther's emotional instability is translated through narrative verbs such as: "*wept aloud*", "*walked in a state of great excitement*", and "*muttering indistinctly*". In Uzbek,

these are transferred with stronger expressive verbs like "*o'ksib-o'ksib yig'ladi*" va "*darg'azab holda*". These choices accelerate the emotional intensity of the character. The repetition structure "*o'ksib-o'ksib*" (sobbing intensely) is more emotionally vivid than the neutral English "wept aloud", suggesting that the translators intentionally improve emotional expressiveness to fit the expectations of Uzbek literary style.

Overall, maintaining emotional effect in literary translation is one of the most challenging aspect of the field. Unlike technical translation, literary translation requires not only linguistic knowledge but also the ability to recreate the emotional atmosphere, stylistic features, and psychological depth of the original work. Translation is therefore both an interpretive and creative process influenced by cultural context and how translators understand the original text.

The comparative analysis of passages from "The Sorrows of Young Werther" by Johann Wolfgang von Goethe and in its Uzbek translation encodes that the translator often prioritizes not literal translation but emotional equivalence. Through the usage of expressive verbs, repetition, and culturally appropriate phrasing, the emotional intensity of the original text is largely maintained.

To conclude, study shows that successful literary translation depends on the translator's ability to balance fidelity to the original text with stylistic and cultural adaptation in order to preserve the emotional impact of the original work.

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